

INFLUENCE OF NEOLOGISMS ON THE UZBEK LANGUAGE

¹Nasiba Xo'janova

Termez State University student, Surkhandarya region,

²Begmatova Durdona Jomg'irovna

Teacher of English language of School №7 in sherabad district,
Surkhandarya region.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7514652>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 27th December 2022

Accepted: 07th January 2023

Online: 08th January 2023

KEY WORDS

Neologisms, brand, trend,
Coworking, IT Center,
mastering words.

ABSTRACT

The scope of application of new words entering the Uzbek language. The positive and negative effects they have on our language.

The Uzbek people are a people with many nationalities and nationalities. From his own head, he experienced dependence, speaking another language and quda-andalik relations with neighboring countries. It must be for this reason that words borrowed from other languages are found in many of our languages. Sometimes we ourselves cannot distinguish in what language our spoken word is. In particular, the Uzbek language is rich in words derived from the Persian language. In the XX century, our vocabulary was significantly enriched even with words that came from the Russian language. Today, however, our language is filled with words borrowed from the English language.

Abdulla Qadiri, a literal native speaker of our native language, wrote: "languages cannot live without borrowing from each other" [1]. We know that our language is enriched by the influence of internal and external sources. Enrichment through internal sources is understood as the literaryization of words related to dialect and the formation of new words by adding suffixes to words, while enrichment through external sources is understood through new words – neologisms, which are now coming from many observed foreign languages. Neologism is a word or speech turnover formed to call a new subject or concept. Neologisms are new words, meanings of a word or a combination of words that are used once in any text or speech acts in a given period in any language. Words such as supermarket, boutique, ayfon, smartphone, brand, trend, hyesh-tag (hashtag), speaker, glamor, which are used in Uzbek language, are new words from the point of view of the period [3]. Of course, it is gratifying that our state has established economic, political and close neighborly relations with many countries in the world. As a result of this, the penetration of foreign words is natural. But the fact that we accept foreign words as an alternative in Uzbekistan without making any changes can cause the weakening of our national language. In particular, taking a look, let's take such a word as Coworking, IT Center, which appeared nearby and began to become popular. So what is Coworking itself? Is there an Uzbek alternative to this word?

Coworking-(English co – work-collaborative work) is a completely different group of people working in different areas, in different companies and projects, a free-form workspace.

Simply put, this is a place where all people can do their job independently, as well as gather to discuss their common project problems and tasks. There are two main reasons why we cannot use this word as a mastering word:

First, the English letters c (si) and w (dablyu) in the word Coworking are not present in our Uzbek Alphabet;

And secondly, I think that it would be more expedient if we find and use this word not for oneself, but for an Uzbek alternative. For example, I think that we will not deviate from the rules of the Uzbek language if instead of this word we call it “Center for cooperation of opinions” or “Center for practical cooperation”.

Now, taking the word IT Center, this word is originally an abbreviation of the English words “Information technological center”, understood as computer technology that performs such tasks as the formation of Information, its collection, distribution, storage, processing, protection. We will not undermine our language if we call this word an alternative in Uzbek, just like the one we mentioned above, that is, not “it Center”, but “information technology center” or “IT Center” for short. In addition, from the appearance of this abbreviation, the Uzbek language indicates an existing dog (puppy, animal).

In conclusion, I think that our acceptance of words coming from a foreign language on the basis of the norms of the Uzbek literary language and the use of their Uzbek-made options will greatly serve to ensure the purity and wealth of our language.

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